
ngsPETSc

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INSTALLATION

To install ngsPETSc you need to clone the GitHub repository, and then you can install it using pip.

```
git clone https://github.com/UZerbinati/ngsPETSc.git
cd ngsPETSc
pip install .
```

Alternatively, you can also build PETSc, SLEPc and NGSolve from source and then install ngsPETSc. First we install all the needed packages using apt and pip or an equivalent package manager.

```
apt-get update
apt-get -y install git build-essential cmake python3 python3-distutils python3-tk
↪ libpython3-dev libxmu-dev tk-dev tcl-dev g++ libglu1-mesa-dev liblapacke-dev libblas-
↪ dev liblapack-dev
pip install numpy cython pytest pytest-mpi
```

We now install PETSc from scratch in a suitable folder, with OpenMPI, HYPRE, Metis, MUMPS, SuprLU, Scalapack and eigen.

```
git clone https://gitlab.com/petsc/petsc.git
cd petsc
python configure --download-chaco \
--download-cmake \
--download-eigen \
--download-openmpi \
--download-hypre \
--download-metis \
--download-parmetis \
--download-ml \
--download-mumps \
--download-scalapack \
--download-superlu_dist \
--with-c2html=0 \
--with-cxx-dialect=C++11 \
--with-debugging=0 \
--download-fblaslapack=1 \
--with-fortran-bindings=0 \
--with-shared-libraries=1 \
--with-petsc4py=1 \
```

To build PETSc you need to run the Makefile as suggested at the end of the configuration script. We now need to set in the .bashrc (on OSX in .bash_profile) file the PETSC_DIR, PETSC_ARCH system variables as they appear when

we finish build PETSc. You also need to add to your PYTHONPATH the PYTHONPATH that appears when we finished building PETSc. We also suggest adding the following line to your `.bashrc` the following lines:

```
export LD_LIBRARY_PATH=$LD_LIBRARY_PATH:$PETSC_DIR/$PETSC_ARCH/lib
export PATH=$PATH:$PETSC_DIR/$PETSC_ARCH/bin
```

We now install SLEPc from source.

```
git clone https://gitlab.com/slepc/slepc.git
cd slepc
python configure --download-blopex --with-slepc4py=1
```

To build SLEPc you need to run the Makefile as suggested at the end of the configuration script. Again set in the `.bashrc` (for MacOS user `.bash_profile`) file the `SLEPC_DIR` system variable as it appears when we finish build SLEPc. You also need to add to your PYTHONPATH the PYTHONPATH that appears when we finished building SLEPc. We now build mpi4py from source in order to have an mpi4py installation that uses PETSc's local MPI installation.

```
git clone https://github.com/mpi4py/mpi4py.git
cd mpi4py
pip install .
```

Now we build NGSolve from source.

```
export BASEDIR=$PWD/ngsuite
mkdir -p $BASEDIR
cd $BASEDIR
git clone https://github.com/NGSolve/ngsolve.git ngsolve-src
cd $BASEDIR/ngsolve-src
git submodule update --init --recursive
mkdir $BASEDIR/ngsolve-build
mkdir $BASEDIR/ngsolve-install
cd $BASEDIR/ngsolve-build
cmake -DCMAKE_INSTALL_PREFIX=${BASEDIR}/ngsolve-install ${BASEDIR}/ngsolve-src -DUSE_
↪MPI=ON
make
make install
```

You should add to your `.bashrc` the `BASEDIR` system variable:

```
echo "export BASEDIR=${BASEDIR}" >> ~/.bashrc
```

We suggest you add the following lines to your `.bashrc`:

```
export NETGENDIR="${BASEDIR}/ngsolve-install/bin"
export PATH=$NETGENDIR:$PATH
export PYTHONPATH=$PYTHONPATH:$NETGENDIR/..`python3 -c "from distutils.sysconfig import_
↪get_python_lib; print(get_python_lib(1,0,''))"`
```

We are now finally ready to install ngsPETSc:

```
git clone https://github.com/UZerbinati/ngsPETSc.git
cd ngsPETSc
NGSPETSC_NO_INSTALL_REQUIRED=ON pip install .
```

**CHAPTER
TWO**

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CHAPTER
THREE

LICENSE

The package is released under the [MIT License](#).

NGSPETSC

ngsPETSc is a NGSolve/Netgen interface to PETSc

4.1 Subpackages

4.1.1 ngsPETSc.utils

Subpackages

`ngsPETSc.utils.firedrake`

Submodules

`ngsPETSc.utils.firedrake.hierarchies`

This module contains all the functions related

Attributes

fd

refinementTypes

Functions

<code>snapToNetgenDMplex</code> (ngmesh, petscPlex)	This function snaps the coordinates of a DMplex mesh to the coordinates of a Netgen mesh.
<code>uniformRefinementRoutine</code> (ngmesh, cdm)	Routing called inside of NetgenHierarchy to compute refined ngmesh and plex.
<code>uniformMapRoutine</code> (meshes)	This function computes the coarse to fine and fine to coarse maps
<code>alfeldRefinementRoutine</code> (ngmesh, cdm)	Routing called inside of NetgenHierarchy to compute refined ngmesh and plex.
<code>alfeldMapRoutine</code> (meshes)	This function computes the coarse to fine and fine to coarse maps
<code>NetgenHierarchy</code> (mesh, levs, flags)	This function creates a Firedrake mesh hierarchy from Netgen/NGSolve meshes.

Module Contents

`ngsPETSc.utils.firedrake.hierarchies.fid = None`

`ngsPETSc.utils.firedrake.hierarchies.snapToNetgenDMplex`(ngmesh, petscPlex)

This function snaps the coordinates of a DMplex mesh to the coordinates of a Netgen mesh.

`ngsPETSc.utils.firedrake.hierarchies.uniformRefinementRoutine`(ngmesh, cdm)

Routing called inside of NetgenHierarchy to compute refined ngmesh and plex.

`ngsPETSc.utils.firedrake.hierarchies.uniformMapRoutine`(meshes)

This function computes the coarse to fine and fine to coarse maps for a uniform mesh hierarchy.

`ngsPETSc.utils.firedrake.hierarchies.alfeldRefinementRoutine`(ngmesh, cdm)

Routing called inside of NetgenHierarchy to compute refined ngmesh and plex.

`ngsPETSc.utils.firedrake.hierarchies.alfeldMapRoutine`(meshes)

This function computes the coarse to fine and fine to coarse maps for a alfeld mesh hierarchy.

`ngsPETSc.utils.firedrake.hierarchies.refinementTypes`

`ngsPETSc.utils.firedrake.hierarchies.NetgenHierarchy`(mesh, levs, flags)

This function creates a Firedrake mesh hierarchy from Netgen/NGSolve meshes.

Parameters

- **mesh** – the Netgen/NGSolve mesh
- **levs** – the number of levels in the hierarchy
- **netgen_flags** – either a bool or a dictionary containing options for Netgen.

If not False the hierarchy is constructed using ngsPETSc, if None hierarchy constructed in a standard manner. Netgen flags includes:

-degree, either an integer denoting the degree of curvature of all levels of the mesh or a list of levs+1 integers denoting the degree of curvature of each level of the mesh. -tol, geometric tolerance adopted in snapToNetgenDMplex. -refinement_type, the refinement type to be used: uniform (default), Alfeld

ngsPETSc.utils.firedrake.meshes

This module contains all the functions related to wrapping NGSolve meshes to Firedrake. We adopt the same docstring convention as the Firedrake project, since this part of the package will only be used in combination with Firedrake.

Attributes

fd

splitTypes

Classes

ngs

dummy class

FiredrakeMesh

This class creates a Firedrake mesh from Netgen/NGSolve meshes.

Functions

flagsUtils(flags, option, default)

utility function used to parse Netgen flag options

refineMarkedElements(self, mark)

This method is used to refine a mesh based on a marking function

curveField(self, order[, tol])

This method returns a curved mesh as a Firedrake function.

splitToQuads(plex, dim, comm)

This method splits a Netgen mesh to quads, using a PETSc transform.

Module Contents

ngsPETSc.utils.firedrake.meshes.f`d` = None

`class` ngsPETSc.utils.firedrake.meshes.ngs

dummy class

`class` comp

dummy class

Mesh

ngsPETSc.utils.firedrake.meshes.f`lagsUtils`(*flags, option, default*)

utility function used to parse Netgen flag options

ngsPETSc.utils.firedrake.meshes.f`refineMarkedElements`(*self, mark*)

This method is used to refine a mesh based on a marking function which is a Firedrake DG0 function.

Parameters

mark – the marking function which is a Firedrake DG0 function.

`ngsPETSc.utils.firedrake.meshes.curveField(self, order, tol=1e-08)`

This method returns a curved mesh as a Firedrake function.

Parameters

order – the order of the curved mesh

`ngsPETSc.utils.firedrake.meshes.splitToQuads(plex, dim, comm)`

This method splits a Netgen mesh to quads, using a PETSc transform. TODO: Improve support quad meshing.

@pef Get netgen to make a quad-dominant mesh, and then only split the triangles.

Current implementation will make for poor-quality meshes.

`ngsPETSc.utils.firedrake.meshes.splitTypes`

`class ngsPETSc.utils.firedrake.meshes.FiredrakeMesh(mesh, netgen_flags, user_comm=fd.COMM_WORLD)`

This class creates a Firedrake mesh from Netgen/NGSolve meshes.

Parameters

- **mesh** – the mesh object, it can be either a Netgen/NGSolve mesh or a PETSc DMplex
- **netgen_flags** – The dictionary of flags to be passed to ngsPETSc.
- **comm** – the MPI communicator.

`createFromTopology(topology, name, comm)`

Internal method to construct a mesh from a mesh topology, copied from Firedrake.

Parameters

- **topology** – the mesh topology
- **name** – the mesh name

ngsPETSc.utils.ngs

Submodules

ngsPETSc.utils.fenicsx

This module contains all the functions related to wrapping NGSolve meshes to FEniCSx. We adopt the same docstring convention as the FEniCSx project, since this part of the package will only be used in combination with FEniCSx.

Attributes

`_ngs_to_cells`

Classes

GeometricModel

This class is used to wrap a Netgen geometric model to a DOLFINx mesh.

Module Contents

ngsPETSc.utils.fenicsx._ngs_to_cells

class ngsPETSc.utils.fenicsx.**GeometricModel**(*geo*, *comm*: *mpi4py.MPI.Comm*)

This class is used to wrap a Netgen geometric model to a DOLFINx mesh. Args:

geo: The Netgen model *comm*: The MPI communicator to use for mesh creation

model_to_mesh(*hmax*: *float*, *gdim*: *int* = 2, *partitioner*: *Callable*[[*mpi4py.MPI.Comm*, *int*, *int*, *dolfinx.cpp.graph.AdjacencysList_int32*], *dolfinx.cpp.graph.AdjacencysList_int32*] = *dolfinx.mesh.create_cell_partitioner*(*dolfinx.mesh.GhostMode.none*), *transform*: *Any* = *None*, *routine*: *Any* = *None*) → *Tuple*[*dolfinx.mesh.Mesh*, *dolfinx.cpp.mesh.MeshTags_int32*, *dolfinx.cpp.mesh.MeshTags_int32*]

Given a NetGen model, take all physical entities of the highest topological dimension and create the corresponding DOLFINx mesh.

This function only works in serial, at the moment.

Args:

hmax: The maximum diameter of the elements in the triangulation model: The NetGen model *gdim*: Geometrical dimension of the mesh *partitioner*: Function that computes the parallel

distribution of cells across MPI ranks

transform: PETSc DMPLEX Transformation to be applied to the mesh *routine*: Function to be applied to the mesh after generation

takes as plan the mesh and the NetGen model and returns the same objects after the routine has been applied.

Returns:

A DOLFINx mesh for the given NetGen model.

4.2 Submodules

4.2.1 ngsPETSc.eps

This module contains all the functions related to the SLEPc eigenvalue solver (EPS/PEP) interface for NGSolve

Attributes

SLEPc

Classes

EigenSolver

This class creates a SLEPc Eigen Problem Solver (EPS/PEP) from NGSolve

Module Contents

`ngsPETSc.eps.SLEPc = None`

class `ngsPETSc.eps.EigenSolver`

This class creates a SLEPc Eigen Problem Solver (EPS/PEP) from NGSolve variational problem pencil, i.e. $a_0(u,v) + \lambda a_1(u,v) + (\lambda^2) a_2(u,v) + \dots = 0$ Inspired by Firedrake Eigensolver class.

Parameters

pencil – tuple containing the bilinear forms $a: V \times V \rightarrow K$ composing

the pencil, e.g. (m,a) with $a = \text{BilinearForm}(\text{grad}(u), \text{grad}(v) * dx)$ and $m = \text{BilinearForm}(-1 * u * v * dx)$

Parameters

- **fes** – finite element space V
- **nev** – number of requested eigenvalue
- **ncv** – dimension of the internal subspace used by SLEPc,

by Default by SLEPc.DECIDE

Parameters

- **solverParameters** – parameters to be passed to the KSP solver
- **optionsPrefix** – special solver options prefix for this specific Krylov solver

4.2.2 ngsPETSc.ksp

This module contains all the functions related to the PETSc linear system solver (KSP) interface for NGSolve

Attributes

parse

Classes

<code>KrylovSolver</code>	This class creates a PETSc Krylov Solver (KSP) for NGSolve.
<code>KSPOperator</code>	This class wraps a PETSc KSP solver as an NGSolve matrix

Functions

<code>createFromBilinearForm(a, freeDofs, solverParameters)</code>	This function creates a PETSc matrix from an NGSolve bilinear form
<code>createFromMatrix(a, freeDofs, solverParameters)</code>	This function creates a PETSc matrix from an NGSolve bilinear form
<code>createFromPC(a, freeDofs, solverParameters)</code>	This function creates a PETSc matrix from an ngsPETSc PETSc Preconditioner
<code>createFromAction(a, freeDofs, solverParameters)</code>	This function creates a matrix free PETSc matrix from an NGSolve matrix

Module Contents

`ngsPETSc.ksp.createFromBilinearForm(a, freeDofs, solverParameters)`

This function creates a PETSc matrix from an NGSolve bilinear form

`ngsPETSc.ksp.createFromMatrix(a, freeDofs, solverParameters)`

This function creates a PETSc matrix from an NGSolve bilinear form

`ngsPETSc.ksp.createFromPC(a, freeDofs, solverParameters)`

This function creates a PETSc matrix from an ngsPETSc PETSc Preconditioner

`ngsPETSc.ksp.createFromAction(a, freeDofs, solverParameters)`

This function creates a matrix free PETSc matrix from an NGSolve matrix

`ngsPETSc.ksp.parse`

class `ngsPETSc.ksp.KrylovSolver(a, dofsDescr, p=None, nullspace=None, optionsPrefix="", solverParameters={})`

This class creates a PETSc Krylov Solver (KSP) for NGSolve. Inspired by Firedrake linear solver class.

Parameters

- **a** – either the bilinear form, `ngs Matrix` or a `petsc4py` matrix
- **dofsDescr** – either finite element space
- **p** – either the bilinear form, `ngs Matrix` or `petsc4py` matrix actin as a preconditioner
- **nullspace** – either a PETSc `NullSpace` or `ngsPETSc PETSc Preconditioner`

or tuple of `ngsPETSc PETSc Preconditioner`.

Parameters

- **solverParameters** – parameters to be passed to the KSP solver
- **optionsPrefix** – special solver options prefix for this specific Krylov solver

solve(*b*, *x*, *mapping=None*)

This function solves the linear system

Parameters

- **b** – right hand side of the linear system
- **x** – solution of the linear system

operator()

This function returns the operator of the KSP solver

class ngsPETSc.ksp.**KSP0peator**(*ksp*)

Bases: ngsolve.la.BaseMatrix

This class wraps a PETSc KSP solver as an NGSolve matrix

Shape()

Shape of the BaseMatrix

CreateVector(*col*)

Create vector corresponding to the matrix

Parameters

- **col** – True if one want a column vector

Mult(*x*, *y*)

Matrix-vector product

4.2.3 ngsPETSc.mat

This module contains all the functions related to wrapping NGSolve matrices to PETSc matrices using the petsc4py interface.

Classes

Matrix

This class creates a PETSc Matrix

Module Contents

class ngsPETSc.mat.**Matrix**(*ngsMat*, *parDescr*, *matType='aij'*, *petscMat=None*)

Bases: object

This class creates a PETSc Matrix

Parameters

- **ngsMat** – the NGSolve matrix
- **freeDofs** – free DOFs of the FE spaces used to construct the matrix
- **matType** – type of PETSc matrix, i.e. PETSc sparse: aij,

MKL sparse: aijmkl or CUDA: aijcusparse

view()

This function display PETSc Mat info

4.2.4 ngsPETSc.nullspace

This module contains all the function and class needed to wrap a PETSc Nullspace in NGSolve

Classes

<i>NullSpace</i>	This class creates a PETSc Null space from NGSolve vectors
------------------	--

Module Contents

class ngsPETSc.nullspace.**NullSpace**(*fes, span, near=False*)

This class creates a PETSc Null space from NGSolve vectors

Parameters

- **fes** – NGSolve finite element space.
- **span** – list NGSolve grid functions spanning the null space.

orthonormalize(*basis*)

Orthonormalize the basis.

4.2.5 ngsPETSc.pc

This module contains all the function and class needed to wrap a PETSc Preconditioner in NGSolve

Classes

<i>PETScPreconditioner</i>	This class creates a Netgen/NGSolve BaseMatrix corresponding to a PETSc PC
<i>ASMPreconditioner</i>	This class creates a Netgen/NGSolve BaseMatrix corresponding to a PETSc ASM PC

Functions

<i>createPETScPreconditioner</i> (mat, freeDofs, solver-Parameters)	Create PETSc PC that can be accessed by NGSolve.
---	--

Module Contents

class ngsPETSc.pc.PETScPreconditioner(*mat, freeDofs, solverParameters=None, optionsPrefix="", nullspace=None, matType='aij'*)

Bases: ngsolve.BaseMatrix

This class creates a Netgen/NGSolve BaseMatrix corresponding to a PETSc PC

Parameters

- **mat** – NGSolve Matrix one would like to build the PETSc preconditioner for.
- **freeDofs** – not constrained degrees of freedom of the finite element space over

which the BilinearForm corresponding to the matrix is defined.

Parameters

- **solverParameters** – parameters to be passed to the KSP solver
- **optionsPrefix** – special solver options prefix for this specific Krylov solver
- **matType** – type of sparse matrix, i.e. PETSc sparse: aij,

MKL sparse: mklaij or CUDA: aijcusparse

Shape()

Shape of the BaseMatrix

CreateVector(*col*)

Create vector corresponding to the matrix

Parameters

- **col** – True if one want a column vector

Mult(*x, y*)

BaseMatrix multiplication $Ax = y$:arg x: vector we are multiplying :arg y: vector we are storing the result in

MultTrans(*x, y*)

BaseMatrix multiplication $A^T x = y$:arg x: vector we are multiplying :arg y: vector we are storing the result in

setActingDofs(*dofs*)

Set the acting dofs of the preconditioner :arg dofs: dofs that the preconditioner is acting on

ngsPETSc.pc.createPETScPreconditioner(*mat, freeDofs, solverParameters*)

Create PETSc PC that can be accessed by NGSolve. :arg mat: NGSolve Matrix one would like to build the PETSc preconditioner for.

Parameters

- **freeDofs** – not constrained degrees of freedom of the finite element space over

which the BilinearForm corresponding to the matrix is defined.

Parameters

- **solverParameters** – parameters to be passed to the KSP solver

class ngsPETSc.pc.ASMPreconditioner(*mat, freeDofs, solverParameters=None, optionsPrefix="", nullspace=None, matType='aij', blocks=None*)

Bases: [PETScPreconditioner](#)

This class creates a Netgen/NGSolve BaseMatrix corresponding to a PETSc ASM PC

Mult(*x*, *y*)

BaseMatrix multiplication $Ax = y$:arg *x*: vector we are multiplying :arg *y*: vector we are storing the result in

MultTrans(*x*, *y*)

BaseMatrix multiplication $A^T x = y$:arg *x*: vector we are multiplying :arg *y*: vector we are storing the result in

4.2.6 ngsPETSc.plex

This module contains all the functions related to wrapping NGSolve meshes to PETSc DMplex using the petsc4py interface.

Attributes

FACE_SETS_LABEL

CELL_SETS_LABEL

EDGE_SETS_LABEL

Classes

ngs

dummy class

MeshMapping

This class creates a mapping between Netgen/NGSolve meshes and PETSc DMplex

Module Contents

class ngsPETSc.plex.ngs

dummy class

class comp

dummy class

Mesh

ngsPETSc.plex.FACE_SETS_LABEL = 'Face Sets'

ngsPETSc.plex.CELL_SETS_LABEL = 'Cell Sets'

ngsPETSc.plex.EDGE_SETS_LABEL = 'Edge Sets'

class ngsPETSc.plex.MeshMapping(*mesh=None, comm=MPI.COMM_WORLD, name='Default'*)

This class creates a mapping between Netgen/NGSolve meshes and PETSc DMplex

Parameters

- **mesh** – the mesh object, it can be either a Netgen/NGSolve mesh or a PETSc DMplex

- **name** – the name of to be assigned to the PETSc DMplex, by default this is set to “Default”

createNGSMesh(*plex*)

This function generate an NGSolve mesh from a PETSc DMplex

Parameters

plex – the PETSc DMplex to be converted in NGSolve mesh object

createPETScDMplex(*mesh*)

This function generate an PETSc DMplex from a Netgen/NGSolve mesh object

Parameters

plex – the Netgen/NGSolve mesh object to be converted into a PETSc DMplex.

4.2.7 ngsPETSc.snes

This module contains all the functions related to the PETSc SNES

Classes

NonLinearSolver

This class creates a PETSc Non-Linear Solver (SNES) from a callback to

Module Contents

class ngsPETSc.snes.**NonLinearSolver**(*fes, a=None, residual=None, objective=None, jacobian=None, solverParameters={}, optionsPrefix=""*)

This class creates a PETSc Non-Linear Solver (SNES) from a callback to a NGSolve residual vector

Parameters

- **fes** – the finite element space over which the non-linear problem is defined
- **a** – the variational form representing the non-linear problem
- **residual** – callback to the residual for the non-linear solver, this fuction is used only if the argument a is None.
- **objective** – callback to the objective for the non-linear solver, this fuction is used only if the argument a is None, if False the PETSSc default is norm 2.
- **jacobian** – callback to the Jacobian for the non-linear solver, this fuction is used only if the argument a is None.

setup(*x0*)

This is method is used to setup the PETSc SNES object

Parameters

x0 – NGSolve grid function representing the initial guess

solve(*x0*)

This is method solves the non-linear problem

Parameters

x0 – NGSolve grid function representing the initial guess

petscResidual(*snes, x, f*)

This method is used to wrap the callback to the residual in a PETSc compatible way

Parameters

- **snes** – PETSc SNES object representing the non-linear solver
- **x** – current guess of the solution as a PETSc Vec
- **f** – residual function as PETSc Vec

abstract residual()

Callback to the residual of the non-linear problem

Parameters

- **x** – current guess of the solution as a PETSc Vec

Returns

the residual as an NGSolve grid function

petscObjective(*snes, x*)

This method is used to wrap the callback to the objective in a PETSc compatible way

Parameters

- **snes** – PETSc SNES object representing the non-linear solver
- **x** – current guess of the solution as a PETSc Vec
- **energy** – energy as a PETSc Scalar

abstract objective()

Callback to the objective of the non-linear problem

Parameters

- **x** – current guess of the solution as a PETSc Vec

Returns

the energy

petscJacobian(*snes, x, J, P*)

This method is used to wrap the callback to the Jacobian in a PETSc compatible way

Parameters

- **snes** – PETSc SNES object representing the non-linear solver
- **x** – current guess of the solution as a PETSc Vec
- **J** – Jacobian computed at x as a PETSc Mat
- **P** – preconditioner for the Jacobian computed at x as a PETSc Mat

abstract jacobian()

Callback to the Jacobian of the non-linear problem

Parameters

- **x** – current guess of the solution as a PETSc Vec

Returns

the Jacobian as an NGSolve matrix

4.2.8 ngsPETSc.vec

This module contains all the functions related to the NGSolve vector - PETSc vector mapping using the petsc4py interface.

Classes

<i>VectorMapping</i>	This class creates a mapping between a PETSc vector and NGSolve
----------------------	---

Module Contents

class `ngsPETSc.vec.VectorMapping`(*parDescr*, *prefix='ngs_'*)

This class creates a mapping between a PETSc vector and NGSolve vectors

Parameters

- **parDescr** – the finite element space for the vector or tuple (dofs, freeDofs)
- **prefix** – prefix for PETSc options

petscVec(*ngsVec*, *petscVec=None*)

This function generate a PETSc vector from a NGSolve vector

Parameters

- **ngsVec** – the NGSolve vector
- **petscVec** – the PETSc vector to be loaded with NGSolve

vector, if None new PETSc vector is generated, by default None.

ngsVec(*petscVec*, *ngsVec=None*)

This function generate a NGSolve vector from a PETSc vector

Parameters

- **petscVec** – the PETSc vector
- **ngsVec** – the NGSolve vector vector to be loaded with PETSc

vector, if None new PETSc vector is generated, by default None.

PRECONDITIONED INVERSE ITERATION FOR LAPLACE EIGENVALUE PROBLEMS

We will use the Preconditioned INVerse ITERation (PINVIT) scheme, developed by [Knyazef and Neymeyr](#), to compute the lowest eigenvalues of the Dirichlet Laplacian. We seek $(u, \lambda) \in H_0^1(\Omega) \times \mathbb{R}$ such that for any $v \in H_0^1(\Omega)$

$$\int_{\Omega} \nabla u \cdot \nabla v \, d\vec{x} = \lambda \int_{\Omega} uv \, d\vec{x}.$$

In the process of coding the PINVIT scheme, we will show how to use the `VectorMapping` class to map PETSc vectors to NGSolve vectors and vice versa. We will also show how to use the `Matrix` class to create a PETSc matrix from an NGSolve `BilinearForm`. First, we need to construct the distributed mesh for the finite element space discretising the PDE.

```
from ngsolve import Mesh, unit_square
import netgen.meshing as ngm
import numpy as np
from scipy.linalg import eigh
from mpi4py.MPI import COMM_WORLD

mesh = Mesh(unit_square.GenerateMesh(maxh=0.2, comm=COMM_WORLD))
```

We now proceed to construct a linear polynomial finite element space, with H^1 conformity, and discretise the mass matrix that represents the L^2 inner product. We also fetch a compatible vector from the mass matrix.

```
from ngsolve import H1, BilinearForm, dx
fes = H1(mesh, order=1, dirichlet="left|right|top|bottom")
u,v = fes.TnT()
m = BilinearForm(u*v*dx).Assemble()
M = m.mat
ngsVec = M.CreateColVector()
```

We are now ready to create a `VectorMapping`, which will first be used to construct a PETSc vector from the `ngsVec` just initialized. The only information that the `VectorMapping` class needs is the finite element space associated to the vector `GridFunction`. This is because the NGSolve `FESpace` class contains information about the way the degrees of freedom are distributed and which degrees of freedom are not constrained by the boundary conditions.

```
from ngsPETSc import VectorMapping
Map = VectorMapping(fes)
petscVec = Map.petscVec(ngsVec)
print("Vector type is {} and it has size {}".format(petscVec.type, petscVec.size))
```

We now use the `Matrix` class to create a PETSc matrix from an NGSolve `BilinearForm`. Once the `Matrix` class has been set up, it is possible to access the corresponding PETSc matrix object as `Matrix().mat`. By default, if `COMM_WORLD.GetSize()` is larger than one, `mat` is initialized as a PETSc `mpiaij` which is the default sparse parallel matrix in PETSc, otherwise `mat` is initialized as a PETSc `seqaij` which is the default serial matrix in PETSc. We can also view the matrix using the `Matrix().view()` method.

```
from ngsPETSc import Matrix
M = Matrix(m.mat, fes)
print("Matrix type is {} and it has size {}".format(M.mat.type,M.mat.size))
M.view()
```

There are other matrix formats available. To mention a few:

- dense, a dense format,
- cusparse, CUDA sparse format, for NVIDIA GPUs.
- ai_jmkl, Intel MKL format.

We solve the discretised problem by looking for the eigenvalues of the generalised eigenproblem $A\vec{u}_h = \lambda M\vec{u}_h$ where A and M are the finite element discretisations respectively of the stiffness matrix for the Laplacian and the mass matrix. Since we have already constructed the mass matrix, it remains to construct the stiffness matrix:

```
from ngsolve import grad, Preconditioner, GridFunction
a = BilinearForm(fes)
a += grad(u)*grad(v)*dx
a.Assemble()
A = Matrix(a.mat, fes)
```

At the heart of the PINVIT scheme there is an iteration similar to the Rayleigh quotient iteration for a generalised eigenvalue problem. More details on the latter can be found in Nick Trefethen's [Numerical Linear Algebra](#), Lecture 27:

$$\vec{u}_h^{(n+1)} = \omega_1^{(n)} \vec{u}_h^{(n)} + \omega_2^{(n)} \vec{\omega}_h^{(n)}, \quad \vec{\omega}_h^{(n)} = P^{-1}(A\vec{u}_h^{(n)} - \rho_n M\vec{u}_h^{(n)}),$$

where P^{-1} is an approximate inverse of the stiffness matrix A , ω_i are step sizes, and ρ_n is the Rayleigh quotient corresponding to $\vec{u}_h^{(n)}$, i.e.

$$\rho_n = \frac{(\vec{u}_h^{(n)}, A\vec{u}_h^{(n)})}{(\vec{u}_h^{(n)}, M\vec{u}_h^{(n)})}.$$

The choice of $\omega_{1,2}^{(n)}$ is important to obtain a convergent PINVIT scheme. We do this by solving the optimization problem,

$$\vec{u}_h^{(n+1)} = \arg \min_{\vec{v} \in \langle \vec{u}_h^{(n)}, \vec{\omega}_h^{(n)} \rangle} \frac{(\vec{u}_h^{(n+1)}, A\vec{u}_h^{(n+1)})}{(\vec{u}_h^{(n+1)}, M\vec{u}_h^{(n+1)})}$$

which is equivalent to a small generalised eigenvalue problem, i.e.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \vec{u}_h^{(n)} \cdot A\vec{u}_h^{(n)} & \vec{u}_h^{(n)} \cdot A\vec{\omega}_h^{(n)} \\ \vec{\omega}_h^{(n)} \cdot A\vec{u}_h^{(n)} & \vec{\omega}_h^{(n)} \cdot A\vec{\omega}_h^{(n)} \end{bmatrix} = \omega \begin{bmatrix} \vec{u}_h^{(n)} \cdot M\vec{u}_h^{(n)} & \vec{u}_h^{(n)} \cdot M\vec{\omega}_h^{(n)} \\ \vec{\omega}_h^{(n)} \cdot M\vec{u}_h^{(n)} & \vec{\omega}_h^{(n)} \cdot M\vec{\omega}_h^{(n)} \end{bmatrix}.$$

```

def stepChoice(Asc,Msc,w,u0):
    Au0 = u0.duplicate(); Asc.mult(u0,Au0)
    Mu0 = u0.duplicate(); Msc.mult(u0,Mu0)
    Aw = w.duplicate(); Asc.mult(w,Aw)
    Mw = w.duplicate(); Msc.mult(w,Mw)
    smallA = np.array([[u0.dot(Au0),u0.dot(Aw)],[w.dot(Au0),w.dot(Aw)]])
    smallM = np.array([[u0.dot(Mu0),u0.dot(Mw)],[w.dot(Mu0),w.dot(Mw)]])
    _, evec = eigh(a=smallA, b=smallM)
    return (float(evec[0,0]),float(evec[1,0]))

```

We then construct a PETSc preconditioner acting as an approximate inverse of A . For this example, we use an algebraic multigrid preconditioner built with HYPRE.

```

from petsc4py import PETSc
pc = PETSc.PC()
pc.create(PETSc.COMM_WORLD)
pc.setOperators(A.mat)
pc.setType(PETSc.PC.Type.HYPRE)
pc.setUp()

```

We now implement the iteration itself:

```

from math import pi
itMax = 10
u0 = A.mat.createVecLeft()
w = A.mat.createVecLeft()
u0.setRandom()
for it in range(itMax):
    Au0 = u0.duplicate(); A.mat.mult(u0,Au0)
    Mu0 = u0.duplicate(); M.mat.mult(u0,Mu0)
    rho = Au0.dot(u0)/Mu0.dot(u0)
    print("[{}] Eigenvalue estimate: {}".format(it,rho/(pi**2)))
    u = Au0+rho*Mu0
    pc.apply(u,w)
    alpha = stepChoice(A.mat,M.mat,w,u0)
    u0 = alpha[0]*u0+alpha[1]*w

```

Table 1: PINVIT Iterations

Iteration	1	2	3	4	5	6
Eigenvalue	7.187387	2.172190	2.133502	2.131257	2.130477	2.130475

SOLVING THE POISSON PROBLEM WITH DIFFERENT PRECONDITIONING STRATEGIES

In this tutorial, we explore using *PETSc KSP* as an out-of-the-box solver inside NGSolve. We will focus our attention on the Poisson problem, and we will consider different solvers and preconditioning strategies. In particular, we will show how to use *MUMPS* as a direct solver, and the use of an incomplete LU factorisation, an algebraic multigrid cycle, and a balancing domain decomposition by constraints (BDDC) approach as preconditioners. We begin considering the Poisson problem on the unit square with Dirichlet boundary conditions on all sides and a right-hand side function $f(x, y) = 32(x(1-x)y(1-y))$, i.e.

$$\text{find } u \in H_0^1(\Omega) \text{ s.t. } a(u, v) := \int_{\Omega} \nabla u \cdot \nabla v \, d\vec{x} = L(v) := \int_{\Omega} f v \, d\vec{x} \quad v \in H_0^1(\Omega).$$

Such a discretisation can easily be constructed using NGSolve as follows:

```
from ngsolve import *
import netgen.gui
import netgen.meshing as ngm
from mpi4py.MPI import COMM_WORLD

if COMM_WORLD.rank == 0:
    ngmesh = unit_square.GenerateMesh(maxh=0.1)
    for _ in range(4):
        ngmesh.Refine()
    mesh = Mesh(ngmesh.Distribute(COMM_WORLD))
else:
    mesh = Mesh(ngm.Mesh.Receive(COMM_WORLD))
order = 2
fes = H1(mesh, order=order, dirichlet="left|right|top|bottom")
print("Number of degrees of freedom: ", fes.ndof)
u, v = fes.TnT()
a = BilinearForm(grad(u)*grad(v)*dx)
f = LinearForm(fes)
f += 32 * (y*(1-y)+x*(1-x)) * v * dx
a.Assemble()
f.Assemble()
```

Now that we have a discretisation of the problem, we use `ngsPETSckrylovSolver` to solve the linear system. The `KrylovSolver` class wraps the PETSc KSP object. We begin showing how to use an LU factorisation as a direct solver, in particular, we use *MUMPS* to perform the factorisation in parallel. Let us discuss the solver options: the flag `"ksp_type"` set to `"preonly"` means that no Krylov method is employed, the flag `"pc_type"` indicates that we use a direct LU factorisation, while `"pc_factor_mat_solver_type"` selects the use of *MUMPS* to perform the LU factorisation.

```

from ngsPETSc import KrylovSolver
solver = KrylovSolver(a, fes.FreeDofs(),
                     solverParameters={"ksp_type": "preonly",
                                       "pc_type": "lu",
                                       "pc_factor_mat_solver_type": "mumps"})

gfu = GridFunction(fes)
solver.solve(f.vec, gfu.vec)
exact = 16*x*(1-x)*y*(1-y)
print ("LU L2-error:", sqrt (Integrate ( (gfu-exact)*(gfu-exact), mesh)))
Draw(gfu)

```

We can also use an iterative solver with an incomplete LU factorisation as a preconditioner. We switch to an iterative solver, setting "ksp_type" to "cg", while we use an incomplete LU factorisation as preconditioner by changing the flag "pc_type". We have also added the flag "ksp_monitor" to view how the residual evolves at each linear iteration.

```

if COMM_WORLD.Get_size() == 1:
    solver = KrylovSolver(a, fes.FreeDofs(),
                        solverParameters={"ksp_type": "cg",
                                        "ksp_monitor": "",
                                        "pc_type": "ilu",
                                        "pc_factor_mat_solver_type": "petsc"})

    gfu = GridFunction(fes)
    solver.solve(f.vec, gfu.vec)
    print ("ILU L2-error:", sqrt (Integrate ( (gfu-exact)*(gfu-exact), mesh)))
    Draw(gfu)
else:
    print("ILU preconditioner is not available in parallel")

```

Table 1: Preconditioner performance

Preconditioner	Iterations
PETSc ILU	166

We can also use an algebraic multigrid preconditioner. In particular, we will use PETSc's own implementation of AMG, *GAMG*. We do this changing the flag "pc_type" to "gamg"

```

solver = KrylovSolver(a, fes.FreeDofs(),
                     solverParameters={"ksp_type": "cg",
                                       "ksp_monitor": "",
                                       "pc_type": "gamg"})

gfu = GridFunction(fes)
solver.solve(f.vec, gfu.vec)
print ("GAMG L2-error:", sqrt (Integrate ( (gfu-exact)*(gfu-exact), mesh)))
Draw(gfu)

```

Table 2: Preconditioner performance

Preconditioner	Iterations
PETSc ILU	166
PETSc GAMG	35

We can also use the PETSc *BDDC* preconditioner. Once again we will select this option via the flag "pc_type" flag.

```

solver = KrylovSolver(a, fes.FreeDofs(),
                    solverParameters={"ksp_type": "cg",
                                      "ksp_monitor": "",
                                      "pc_type": "bddc",
                                      "ngs_mat_type": "is"})

gfu = GridFunction(fes)
solver.solve(f.vec, gfu.vec)
print ("BDDC L2-error:", sqrt (Integrate ( (gfu-exact)*(gfu-exact), mesh)))
Draw(gfu)

```

Table 3: Preconditioner performance

Preconditioner	Iterations
PETSc ILU	166
PETSc GAMG	35
PETSc BDDC (N=2)	5
PETSc BDDC (N=4)	7
PETSc BDDC (N=6)	9

We can see that for an increasing number of subdomains N the number of iterations also increases. Notice that in all the cases we have considered, the `KrylovSolver` class creates a PETSc matrix from the NGSolve matrix in order to assemble the required preconditioners. If we have already some knowledge of the preconditioner we want to use, we can use the `KrylovSolver` class in a matrix-free fashion. This will result in a faster setup time and less memory usage. We will now use the `KrylovSolver` class in a matrix-free fashion with the element-wise BDDC preconditioner implemented in NGSolve.

```

a = BilinearForm(grad(u)*grad(v)*dx)
el_bddc = Preconditioner(a, "bddc")
a.Assemble()
solver = KrylovSolver(a.mat, fes.FreeDofs(), p=el_bddc.mat,
                    solverParameters={"ksp_type": "cg",
                                      "ksp_monitor": "",
                                      "pc_type": "mat",
                                      "ngs_mat_type": "python",
                                      "ksp_rtol": 1e-10})

gfu = GridFunction(fes)
solver.solve(f.vec, gfu.vec)
print ("Element-wise BDDC L2-error:", sqrt (Integrate ( (gfu-exact)*(gfu-exact), mesh)))
Draw(gfu)

```

Table 4: Preconditioner performance

Preconditioner	Iterations
PETSc ILU	166
PETSc GAMG	35
PETSc BDDC (N=2)	5
PETSc BDDC (N=4)	7
PETSc BDDC (N=6)	9
Element-wise BDDC	14

SOLVING LINEAR ELASTICITY WITH A NEAR NULLSPACE

In this tutorial, we explore a linear elasticity discretisation. As we did in *Solving the Poisson problem with different preconditioning strategies*, we will solve the linear system arising from the discretisation using a *PETSc KSP*. We begin by creating a discretisation for the weak formulation of linear elasticity with Lamé coefficients μ and λ , i.e. find $\vec{u} \in [H_0^1(\Omega)]^d$ such that

$$a(u, v) := 2\mu \int_{\Omega} \epsilon(\vec{u}) : \epsilon(\vec{v}) \, d\vec{x} + \lambda \int_{\Omega} (\nabla \cdot \vec{u}) \, d\vec{x} = L(v) := \int_{\Omega} f v \, d\vec{x} \quad \vec{v} \in [H_0^1(\Omega)]^d.$$

We can easily discretise this problem using NGSolve:

```

from ngsolve import *
import netgen.gui
import netgen.meshing as ngm
from mpi4py.MPI import COMM_WORLD

mesh = Mesh(unit_square.GenerateMesh(maxh=0.1, comm=COMM_WORLD))

E, nu = 210, 0.2
mu = E / 2 / (1+nu)
lam = E * nu / ((1+nu)*(1-2*nu))

def Stress(strain):
    return 2*mu*strain + lam*Trace(strain)*Id(2)

fes = VectorH1(mesh, order=1, dirichlet="left")
u, v = fes.TnT()

a = BilinearForm(InnerProduct(Stress(Sym(Grad(u))), Sym(Grad(v))))*dx
a.Assemble()

force = CF( (0,1) )
f = LinearForm(force*v*ds("right")).Assemble()

```

We begin solving the linear system using PETSc's own implementation of an algebraic multigrid preconditioner.

```

from ngsPETSc import KrylovSolver
opts = {'ksp_type': 'cg',
        'ksp_monitor': None,
        'pc_type': 'gamg'}
solver = KrylovSolver(a, fes, solverParameters=opts)
gfu = GridFunction(fes, name="gfu")

```

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```
solver.solve(f.vec, gfu.vec)
Draw (gfu)
```

Table 1: Preconditioner performance for PETSc GAMG.

Preconditioner	Iterations
PETSc GAMG	19 (6.27e-08)

To improve the performance of *PETSc GAMG* we pass it the near-null space composed of the rigid body motions. Using the `near` flag we tell *PETSc KSP* to pass the nullspace as a near nullspace to *PETSc GAMG*.

```
from ngsPETSc import NullSpace
rbms = []
for val in [(1,0), (0,1), (-y,x)]:
    rbm = GridFunction(fes)
    rbm.Set(CF(val))
    rbms.append(rbm.vec)
nullspace = NullSpace(fes, rbms, near=True)
opts = {'ksp_type': 'cg',
        'pc_monitor': None,
        'pc_type': 'gamg'}
solver = KrylovSolver(a, fes, solverParameters=opts, nullspace=nullspace)
gfu = GridFunction(fes, name="gfu_near")
solver.solve(f.vec, gfu.vec)
Draw (gfu)
```

Table 2: Preconditioner performance for PETSc GAMG.

Preconditioner	Iterations
PETSc GAMG	19 (6.27e-08)
PETSc GAMG (with near nullspace)	6 (4.55e-07)

VERTEX PATCH SMOOTHING FOR P-MULTIGRID PRECONDITIONERS FOR THE POISSON PROBLEM

In this tutorial, we explore using *PETSc PC* as a building block inside the NGSolve preconditioning infrastructure. Not all the preconditioning strategies are equally effective for the discretisations of the Poisson problem here considered. This demo is intended to provide a starting point for the exploration of preconditioning strategies rather than providing a definitive answer. We begin by creating a discretisation of the Poisson problem using H1 elements, in particular, we consider the usual variational formulation

$$\text{find } u \in H_0^1(\Omega) \text{ s.t. } a(u, v) := \int_{\Omega} \nabla u \cdot \nabla v \, d\vec{x} = L(v) := \int_{\Omega} f v \, d\vec{x} \quad v \in H_0^1(\Omega).$$

Such a discretisation can easily be constructed using NGSolve as follows:

```
from ngsolve import *
import netgen.gui
import netgen.meshing as ngm
from mpi4py.MPI import COMM_WORLD

if COMM_WORLD.rank == 0:
    ngmesh = unit_square.GenerateMesh(maxh=0.1)
    for _ in range(4):
        ngmesh.Refine()
    mesh = Mesh(ngmesh.Distribute(COMM_WORLD))
else:
    mesh = Mesh(ngm.Mesh.Receive(COMM_WORLD))
order = 2
fes = H1(mesh, order=order, dirichlet="left|right|top|bottom")
print("Number of degrees of freedom: ", fes.ndof)
u, v = fes.TnT()
a = BilinearForm(grad(u)*grad(v)*dx)
f = LinearForm(fes)
f += 32 * (y*(1-y)+x*(1-x)) * v * dx
a.Assemble()
f.Assemble()
```

We now construct an NGSolve preconditioner wrapping a *PETSc PC* object. In particular, we begin considering an algebraic multigrid preconditioner constructed using *HYPRE*. We will use the preconditioner just discussed inside NGSolve's own linear algebra solvers.

```
from ngsPETSc.pc import *
from ngsolve.krylovspace import CG
pre = Preconditioner(a, "PETScPC", pc_type="hypre")
```

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```

gfu = GridFunction(fes)
print("-----|HYPRE p={}|-----".format(order))
gfu.vec.data = CG(a.mat, rhs=f.vec, pre=pre.mat, printrates=True)
Draw(gfu)

```

We see that the HYPRE preconditioner is quite effective for the Poisson problem discretised using linear elements, but it is not as effective for higher-order elements.

Table 1: Preconditioners performance HYPRE

Preconditioner	p=1	p=2	p=3	p=4
HYPRE	10 (1.57e-12)	70 (2.22e-13)	42 (3.96e-13)	70 (1.96e-13)

To overcome this issue we will use a two-level additive Schwarz preconditioner. In this case, we will use as fine space correction the inverse of the stiffness matrices associated with the patch of a vertex.

```

def VertexPatchBlocks(mesh, fes):
    blocks = []
    freedofs = fes.FreeDofs()
    for v in mesh.vertices:
        vdofs = set()
        for el in mesh[v].elements:
            vdofs |= set(d for d in fes.GetDofNrs(el)
                        if freedofs[d])
        blocks.append(vdofs)
    return blocks

blocks = VertexPatchBlocks(mesh, fes)
dofs = BitArray(fes.ndof); dofs[:] = True
blockjac = ASMPreconditioner(a.mat, dofs, blocks=blocks,
                             solverParameters={"pc_type": "asm",
                                                "sub_ksp_type": "preonly",
                                                "sub_pc_type": "lu"})

```

We now isolate the degrees of freedom associated with the vertices and construct a two-level additive Schwarz preconditioner, where the coarse space correction is the inverse of the stiffness matrices associated with the vertices.

```

def VertexDofs(mesh, fes):
    vertextdofs = BitArray(fes.ndof)
    vertextdofs[:] = False
    for v in mesh.vertices:
        for d in fes.GetDofNrs(v):
            vertextdofs[d] = True
    vertextdofs &= fes.FreeDofs()
    return vertextdofs

vertextdofs = VertexDofs(mesh, fes)
preCoarse = PETScPreconditioner(a.mat, vertextdofs, solverParameters={"pc_type": "hypre"})
pretwo = preCoarse + blockjac
print("-----|Additive Schwarz p={}|-----".format(order))
gfu.vec.data = CG(a.mat, rhs=f.vec, pre=pretwo, printrates=True)

```

We can see that the two-level additive Schwarz preconditioner where the coarse space correction is performed using HYPRE is more effective than using just HYPRE for higher-order elements.

Table 2: Preconditioners performance HYPRE and Two Level Additive Schwarz

Preconditioner	p=1	p=2	p=3	p=4
HYPRE	10 (1.57e-12)	70 (2.22e-13)	42 (3.96e-13)	70 (1.96e-13)
Additive Schwarz	44 (1.96e-12)	45 (1.28e-12)	45 (1.29e-12)	45 (1.45e-12)

AUGMENTED LAGRANGIAN PRECONDITIONING FOR P2-P0 DISCRETISATION OF THE STOKES PROBLEM

In this tutorial, we explore constructing preconditioners for discretisations of the Stokes problem with Boffi-Lovadina augmentation. In particular, we will consider a P2-P0 inf-sup stable discretisation of the Stokes problem, i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{find } (\vec{u}, p) \in [H_0^1(\Omega)]^d \times L^2(\Omega) \text{ s.t.} \\ & \begin{cases} (\nabla \vec{u}, \nabla \vec{v})_{L^2(\Omega)} + (\nabla \cdot \vec{v}, p)_{L^2(\Omega)} = (\vec{f}, \vec{v})_{L^2(\Omega)} & \forall v \in H_0^1(\Omega) \\ (\nabla \cdot \vec{u}, q)_{L^2(\Omega)} = 0 & \forall q \in L^2(\Omega) \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Such a discretisation can easily be constructed using NGSolve as follows:

```
from ngsolve import *
from netgen.occ import *
import netgen.gui
import netgen.meshing as ngm
from mpi4py.MPI import COMM_WORLD

if COMM_WORLD.rank == 0:
    shape = Rectangle(2,0.41).Circle(0.2,0.2,0.05).Reverse().Face()
    shape.edges.name="wall"
    shape.edges.Min(X).name="inlet"
    shape.edges.Max(X).name="outlet"
    geo = OCCGeometry(shape, dim=2)
    ngmesh = geo.GenerateMesh(maxh=0.1)
    mesh = Mesh(ngmesh.Distribute(COMM_WORLD))
else:
    mesh = Mesh(ngm.Mesh.Receive(COMM_WORLD))
nu = Parameter(1.0)
V = VectorH1(mesh, order=2, dirichlet="wall|inlet|cyl", autoupdate=True)
Q = L2(mesh, order=0, autoupdate=True)
u,v = V.TnT(); p,q = Q.TnT()
a = BilinearForm(nu*InnerProduct(Grad(u), Grad(v))*dx)
a.Assemble()
b = BilinearForm(div(u)*q*dx)
b.Assemble()
gfu = GridFunction(V, name="u")
gfp = GridFunction(Q, name="p")
uin = CoefficientFunction( (1.5*4*y*(0.41-y)/(0.41*0.41), 0) )
gfu.Set(uin, definedon=mesh.Boundaries("inlet"))
f = LinearForm(V).Assemble()
g = LinearForm(Q).Assemble();
```

We can now explore what happens if we use a Schur complement preconditioner for the saddle point problem. We can construct the (dense!) Schur complement preconditioner using the following code:

```
K = BlockMatrix( [ [a.mat, b.mat.T], [b.mat, None] ] )
from ngsPETSc.pc import *
apre = Preconditioner(a, "PETScPC", pc_type="lu")
S = (b.mat @ apre.mat @ b.mat.T).ToDense().NumPy()
from numpy.linalg import inv
from scipy.sparse import coo_matrix
from ngsolve.la import SparseMatrixd
Sinv = coo_matrix(inv(S))
Sinv = la.SparseMatrixd.CreateFromCOO(indi=Sinv.row,
                                     indj=Sinv.col,
                                     values=Sinv.data,
                                     h=S.shape[0],
                                     w=S.shape[1])
C = BlockMatrix( [ [a.mat.Inverse(V.FreeDofs()), None],
                  [None, Sinv] ] )

rhs = BlockVector ( [f.vec, g.vec] )
sol = BlockVector( [gfu.vec, gfp.vec] )
print("-----|Schur|-----")
solvers.MinRes (mat=K, pre=C, rhs=rhs, sol=sol, tol=1e-8,
                printrates=True, initialize=False)
Draw(gfu)
```

The Schur complement preconditioner converges in a few iterations, but as written it is not very efficient since we need to assemble and invert the dense Schur complement.

Table 1: Preconditioner performance

Preconditioner	Iterations
Schur complement	4 (9.15e-14)

Since our discretisation is inf-sup stable it is possible to prove that the mass matrix of the pressure space is spectrally equivalent to the Schur complement. This means that we can use the mass matrix of the pressure space as a preconditioner for the Schur complement. Notice that we still need to invert the mass matrix and we will do so using a *PETSc PC* of type Jacobi, which is the exact inverse since we are using *P0* pressure elements. We will also invert the Laplacian block using a *PETSc PC* of type *LU*.

```
m = BilinearForm((1/nu)*p*q*dx).Assemble()
mpre = Preconditioner(m, "PETScPC", pc_type="jacobi")
apre = a.mat.Inverse(V.FreeDofs())
C = BlockMatrix( [ [apre, None], [None, mpre] ] )

gfu.vec.data[:] = 0; gfp.vec.data[:] = 0;
gfu.Set(uin, definedon=mesh.Boundaries("inlet"))
sol = BlockVector( [gfu.vec, gfp.vec] )

print("-----|Mass & LU|-----")
solvers.MinRes (mat=K, pre=C, rhs=rhs, sol=sol, tol=1e-8,
                maxsteps=100, printrates=True, initialize=False)
Draw(gfu)
```

Table 2: Preconditioner performance

Preconditioner	Iterations
Schur complement	4 (9.15e-14)
Mass & LU	66 (2.45e-08)

We can also construct a multi-grid preconditioner for the top left block of the saddle point problem, as we have seen in *Vertex Patch smoothing for p-Multigrid preconditioners for the Poisson problem*.

```
def DoFInfo(mesh, fes):
    blocks = []
    freedofs = fes.FreeDofs()
    vertexdofs = BitArray(fes.ndof)
    vertexdofs[:] = False
    for v in mesh.vertices:
        vdofs = set()
        vdofs |= set(d for d in fes.GetDofNrs(v) if freedofs[d])
        for ed in mesh[v].edges:
            vdofs |= set(d for d in fes.GetDofNrs(ed) if freedofs[d])
        for fc in mesh[v].faces:
            vdofs |= set(d for d in fes.GetDofNrs(fc) if freedofs[d])
        blocks.append(vdofs)
        for d in fes.GetDofNrs(v):
            vertexdofs[d] = True
    vertexdofs &= fes.FreeDofs()
    return vertexdofs, blocks

vertexdofs, blocks = DoFInfo(mesh, V)
blockjac = a.mat.CreateBlockSmoother(blocks)
preH = PETScPreconditioner(a.mat, vertexdofs, solverParameters={"pc_type": "hypre"})
twolvpre = preH + blockjac
C = BlockMatrix( [ [twolvpre, None], [None, mpre] ] )
gfu.vec.data[:] = 0; gfp.vec.data[:] = 0;
gfu.Set(uin, definedon=mesh.Boundaries("inlet"))
print("-----|Mass & Two Level Additive Schwarz|-----")
solvers.MinRes (mat=K, pre=C, rhs=rhs, sol=sol, tol=1e-8,
                maxsteps=100, printrates=True, initialize=False)
```

Table 3: Preconditioner performance

Preconditioner	Iterations
Schur complement	4 (9.15e-14)
Mass & LU	66 (2.45e-08)
Mass & Two Level Additive Schwarz	100 (4.68e-06)

The preconditioner constructed so far doesn't seem to be ideal, in fact, our Krylov solver took many iterations to converge with a direct LU factorisation of the velocity block and did not converge at all with *HYPRE*. To resolve this issue we resort to an augmented Lagrangian formulation, i.e.

$$\begin{cases} (\nabla \vec{u}, \nabla \vec{v})_{L^2(\Omega)} + (\nabla \cdot \vec{v}, p)_{L^2(\Omega)} + \gamma (\nabla \cdot \vec{u}, \nabla \cdot \vec{v})_{L^2(\Omega)} = (\vec{f}, \vec{v})_{L^2(\Omega)} & \forall v \in H_0^1(\Omega) \\ (\nabla \cdot \vec{u}, q)_{L^2(\Omega)} = 0 & \forall q \in L^2(\Omega) \end{cases}$$

This formulation can easily be constructed in NGSolve, as follows:

```

gamma = Parameter(1e6)
aG = BilinearForm(nu*InnerProduct(Grad(u), Grad(v))*dx+gamma*div(u)*div(v)*dx)
aG.Assemble()
aGpre = Preconditioner(aG, "PETScPC", pc_type="lu")
mG = BilinearForm((1/nu+gamma)*p*q*dx).Assemble()
mGpre = Preconditioner(mG, "PETScPC", pc_type="jacobi")

K = BlockMatrix( [ [aG.mat, b.mat.T], [b.mat, None] ] )
C = BlockMatrix( [ [aGpre.mat, None], [None, mGpre.mat] ] )

gfu.vec.data[:] = 0; gfp.vec.data[:] = 0;
gfu.Set(uin, definedon=mesh.Boundaries("inlet"))
sol = BlockVector( [gfu.vec, gfp.vec] )

print("-----|Boffi--Lovadina Augmentation LU|-----")
solvers.MinRes (mat=K, pre=C, rhs=rhs, sol=sol, tol=1e-10,
                printrates=True, initialize=False)
Draw(gfu)

```

Using an augmented Lagrangian formulation and a direct inversion of the velocity block, we were able to converge in only two iterations. This is because the augmented Lagrangian formulation improves the spectral equivalence between the mass matrix of the pressure space and the Schur complement.

Table 4: Preconditioner performance

Preconditioner	Iterations
Schur complement	4 (9.15e-14)
Mass & LU	66 (2.45e-08)
Mass & Two Level Additive Schwarz	100 (4.68e-06)
Augmented Lagrangian LU	2 (9.24e-8)

Notice that so far we have been inverting the matrix corresponding to the Laplacian block using a direct LU factorisation. This is not ideal for large problems, and we can try to use a *HYPRE* preconditioner for the Laplacian block.

```

smoother = aG.mat.CreateBlockSmoother(blocks)
preHG = PETScPreconditioner(aG.mat, vertextdofs, solverParameters={"pc_type":"hybre"})
twolvpre = preHG + smoother
C = BlockMatrix( [ [twolvpre, None], [None, mGpre] ] )
gfu.vec.data[:] = 0; gfp.vec.data[:] = 0;
gfu.Set(uin, definedon=mesh.Boundaries("inlet"))
print("-----|Boffi--Lovadina Augmentation Two Level Additive Schwarz|-----")
solvers.MinRes (mat=K, pre=C, rhs=rhs, sol=sol, tol=1e-10,
                printrates=True, initialize=False)
Draw(gfu)

```

Table 5: Preconditioner performance

Preconditioner	Iterations
Schur complement	4 (9.15e-14)
Mass & LU	66 (2.45e-08)
Mass & Two Level Additive Schwarz	100 (4.68e-06)
Augmented Lagrangian LU	2 (9.24e-08)
Augmented Two Level Additive Schwarz	100 (1.06e-03)

Our first attempt at using a *HYPRE* preconditioner for the Laplacian block did not converge. This is because the top left block of the saddle point problem now contains the augmentation term, which has a very large kernel. It is well known that algebraic multi-grid methods do not work well for such problems, and this is what we are observing here. We begin by constructing the augmented Lagrangian formulation in more numerical linear algebra terms, i.e.

$$\begin{bmatrix} A + B^T(\gamma M^{-1})B & B^T \\ B & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u \\ p \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} f \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

We can construct this linear algebra problem inside NGSolve as follows:

```
d = BilinearForm((1/gamma)*p*q*dx)
d.Assemble()
dpre = PETScPreconditioner(d.mat, Q.FreeDofs(), solverParameters={"pc_type":"lu"})
aG = a.mat + b.mat.T@dpre@b.mat
aG = coo_matrix(aG.ToDense().NumPy())
aG = la.SparseMatrixd.CreateFromCOO(indi=aG.row,
                                   indj=aG.col,
                                   values=aG.data,
                                   h=aG.shape[0],
                                   w=aG.shape[1])
K = BlockMatrix( [ [aG, b.mat.T], [b.mat, None] ] )
pre = PETScPreconditioner(aG, V.FreeDofs(), solverParameters={"pc_type":"lu"})
C = BlockMatrix( [ [pre, None], [None, mGpre.mat] ] )

gfu.vec.data[:] = 0; gfp.vec.data[:] = 0;
gfu.Set(uin, definedon=mesh.Boundaries("inlet"))
sol = BlockVector( [gfu.vec, gfp.vec] )

print("-----|Boffi--Lovadina Augmentation LU|-----")
solvers.MinRes (mat=K, pre=C, rhs=rhs, sol=sol, tol=1e-10,
               prinrates=True, initialize=False)
Draw(gfu)
```

Since the augmentation block has a lower rank than the Laplacian block, we can use the Sherman-Morrison-Woodbury formula to invert the augmentation block.

$$(A + B^T(\gamma M^{-1})B)^{-1} = A^{-1} - A^{-1}B^T\left(\frac{1}{\gamma}M^{-1} + BA^{-1}B^T\right)^{-1}BA^{-1}$$

We will do this in two different ways first we will invert the $(\frac{1}{\gamma}M^{-1} + BA^{-1}B^T)$ block using a direct LU factorisation. Then we will notice that since the penalisation parameter is large we can ignore the $\frac{1}{\gamma}M^{-1}$ term and use the mass matrix since it is spectrally equivalent to the Schur complement.

```
SM = (d.mat + b.mat@apre@b.mat.T).ToDense().NumPy()
SM = coo_matrix(SM)
```

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```

SM = la.SparseMatrixd.CreateFromCOO(indi=SM.row,
                                   indj=SM.col,
                                   values=SM.data,
                                   h=SM.shape[0],
                                   w=SM.shape[1])

SMinv = PETScPreconditioner(SM, Q.FreeDofs(), solverParameters={"pc_type":"lu"})

C = BlockMatrix( [ [apre - apre@b.mat.T@SMinv@b.mat@apre, None], [None, mGpre.mat] ] )

gfu.vec.data[:] = 0; gfp.vec.data[:] = 0;
gfu.Set(uin, definedon=mesh.Boundaries("inlet"))
sol = BlockVector( [gfu.vec, gfp.vec] )

print("-----|Boffi--Lovadina Augmentation Sherman-Morrison-Woodbury|-----")
solvers.MinRes (mat=K, pre=C, rhs=rhs, sol=sol, tol=1e-10,
               printrates=True, initialize=False)
Draw(gfu)

C = BlockMatrix( [ [apre + apre@(b.mat.T@mGpre.mat@b.mat)@apre, None], [None, mGpre.mat] ] )
↪ ] )

gfu.vec.data[:] = 0; gfp.vec.data[:] = 0;
gfu.Set(uin, definedon=mesh.Boundaries("inlet"))
sol = BlockVector( [gfu.vec, gfp.vec] )

print("-----|Boffi--Lovadina Augmentation Sherman-Morrison-Woodbury|-----")
solvers.MinRes (mat=K, pre=C, rhs=rhs, sol=sol, tol=1e-13,
               printrates=True, initialize=False)
Draw(gfu)

```

We see that a purely algebraic approach based on the Sherman-Morrison-Woodbury formula is more efficient for the augmented Lagrangian formulation than a naive two-level additive Schwarz approach.

Table 6: Preconditioner performance

Preconditioner	Iterations
Schur complement	4 (9.15e-14)
Mass & LU	66 (2.45e-08)
Mass & Two Level Additive Schwarz	100 (4.68e-06)
Augmented Lagrangian LU	2 (9.24e-08)
Augmented Two Level Additive Schwarz	100 (1.06e-03)
Augmentation Schermon-Morrison-Woodbury	84 (1.16e-07)

VERTEX PATCH SMOOTHING FOR AUGMENTED LAGRANGIAN FORMULATIONS OF THE OSEEN PROBLEM

In this tutorial, we will see how to use an augmented Lagrangian formulation to precondition the Oseen problem, i.e.

Given $\vec{\beta} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ find $(\vec{u}, p) \in [H_0^1(\Omega)]^d \times L^2(\Omega)$ s.t.

$$\begin{cases} \nu(\nabla \vec{u}, \nabla \vec{v})_{L^2(\Omega)} + (\nabla \cdot \vec{v}, p)_{L^2(\Omega)} - (\nabla \vec{u} \vec{\beta}, \vec{v})_{L^2(\Omega)} + \gamma(\operatorname{div}(\vec{u}), \operatorname{div}(\vec{v}))_{L^2(\Omega)} = (\vec{f}, \vec{v})_{L^2(\Omega)} & \forall v \in H_0^1(\Omega) \\ (\nabla \cdot \vec{u}, q)_{L^2(\Omega)} = 0 & \forall q \in L^2(\Omega) \end{cases}$$

Let us begin defining the parameters of the problem.

```
from ngsolve import *
from ngsPETSc import *
nu = 1e-4; gamma = 1e8
nu = Parameter(nu)
gamma = Parameter(gamma)
b = CoefficientFunction((4*(2*y-1)*(1-x)*x, -4*(2*x-1)*(1-y)*y))
uin = CoefficientFunction((1,0))
```

In particular, we will consider a high-order Hood-Taylor discretisation of the problem. Such a discretisation can easily be constructed using NGSolve as follows:

```
from netgen.occ import *
import netgen.gui
import netgen.meshing as ngm
from ngsolve.meshes import MakeStructured2DMesh
from mpi4py.MPI import COMM_WORLD

if COMM_WORLD.rank == 0:
    ngmesh = MakeStructured2DMesh(False, 40, 40).ngmesh
    mesh = Mesh(ngmesh.Distribute(COMM_WORLD))
else:
    mesh = Mesh(ngm.Mesh.Receive(COMM_WORLD))
V = H1(mesh, order=4, hoprolongation=True, dirichlet=".*")
V = V**mesh.dim
Q = L2(mesh, order=3)
u,v = V.TnT(); p,q = Q.TnT()
a = BilinearForm(nu*InnerProduct(Grad(u), Grad(v))*dx)
a += InnerProduct(Grad(u)*b, v)*dx
a += gamma*div(u)*div(v)*dx
b = BilinearForm(div(u)*q*dx)
c = BilinearForm(-1e-10*p*q*dx)
```

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```
f = LinearForm(V)
g = LinearForm(Q)
```

In *Augmented Lagrangian preconditioning for P2-P0 discretisation of the Stokes problem* we have seen that augmenting the Stokes linear system with a $\gamma(\operatorname{div}(\vec{u}), \operatorname{div}(\vec{v}))_{L^2(\Omega)}$ we can obtain better converge result for a field-split preconditioner where we use the pressure mass matrix instead of the Schur complement.

```
mG = BilinearForm((1/nu+gamma)*p*q*dx)
```

We can now assemble the matrices and the right-hand side of the problem.

```
from ngsPETSc.pc import *
a.Assemble()
aCoarsePre = PETScPreconditioner(a.mat, V.FreeDofs(),
                                solverParameters={"pc_type": "lu"})

for l in range(2):
    if l != 0: mesh.Refine()
V.Update(); Q.Update()
dofs = BitArray(V.ndof+Q.ndof); dofs[:] = True
a.Assemble(); b.Assemble(); mG.Assemble();
f.Assemble(); g.Assemble(); c.Assemble();
prol = V.Prolongation().Operator(1)
mGpre = PETScPreconditioner(mG.mat, Q.FreeDofs(),
                            solverParameters={"pc_type": "lu"})
K = BlockMatrix( [ [a.mat, b.mat.T], [b.mat, c.mat] ] )
```

As discussed in *Augmented Lagrangian preconditioning for P2-P0 discretisation of the Stokes problem*, the hard part remains the construction of $(A + \gamma B^T M^{-1} B)^{-1}$ to precondition the (1,1) block. We will use a two-level additive Schwarz preconditioner made of an exact coarse correction and a vertex patch smoother, similar to what we presented in *Vertex Patch smoothing for p-Multigrid preconditioners for the Poisson problem*. Notice that while the smoother is very similar to the one used in *Vertex Patch smoothing for p-Multigrid preconditioners for the Poisson problem*, for the coarse correction we are here using h-multigrid and not p-multigrid.

```
def VertexStarPatchBlocks(mesh, fes):
    blocks = []
    freedofs = fes.FreeDofs()
    for v in mesh.vertices:
        vdofs = set(d for d in fes.GetDofNrs(v) if freedofs[d])
        for ed in mesh[v].edges:
            vdofs |= set(d for d in fes.GetDofNrs(ed) if freedofs[d])
        blocks.append(vdofs)
    return blocks

blocks = VertexStarPatchBlocks(mesh, V)
dofs = BitArray(V.ndof); dofs[:] = True
smoother = ASMPreconditioner(a.mat, dofs, blocks=blocks,
                             solverParameters={"pc_type": "asm",
                                                "sub_ksp_type": "preonly",
                                                "sub_pc_type": "lu"})

prol = V.Prolongation().Operator(1)
two_lv = prol@ aCoarsePre @ prol.T + smoother
C = BlockMatrix( [ [two_lv, None], [None, mGpre] ] )
print("-----|Additive h-Multigrid + Vertex star smoothing|-----")
```

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```

gfu = GridFunction(V, name='AdditiveVel'); gfp = GridFunction(Q, name='AdditivePres')
gfu.vec.data[:] = 0; gfp.vec.data[:] = 0
gfu.Set(uin, definedon=mesh.Boundaries("top"))
rhs = BlockVector( [f.vec, g.vec] )
sol = BlockVector( [gfu.vec, gfp.vec] )
rhs -= K * sol
dofs = BitArray(V.ndof+Q.ndof); dofs[:] = True
solver = KrylovSolver(K,dofs, p=C,
                    solverParameters={"ksp_type": "gmres",
                                       "ksp_max_it":100,
                                       "ksp_monitor_true_residual": None,
                                       "ksp_rtol": 1e-6,
                                       "pc_type": "mat"
                                       })

solver.solve(rhs, sol)
gfu0 = GridFunction(V, name="PETSc0"); gfp0 = GridFunction(Q)
gfu0.vec.data[:] = 0
gfu0.Set(uin, definedon=mesh.Boundaries("top"))
sol0 = BlockVector( [gfu0.vec, gfp0.vec] )
sol += sol0
gfu.vec.data = sol[0]
Draw(gfu)
vtk = VTKOutput(ma=mesh, coefs=[gfu],
               names = ["velocity"],
               filename="output/0seen_{}".format(nu.Get()),
               subdivision=0)
vtk.Do()

```

Table 1: Preconditioner performance for different values of the Reynolds number, for a fixed penalty parameter $\gamma = 10^8$

Raynolds number	1e-2	1e-3	1e-4
Augmented Lagrangian preconditioner	2 (1.57e-5)	3 (7.44e-6)	5 (6.59e-6)

NON-LINEAR SIMULATION OF A HYPERELASTIC BEAM

We consider a simple beam with a hyperelastic material model. In particular, we will assume the beam has energy:

$$E(u) := \int_{\Omega} \frac{\mu}{2} \text{tr}(\mathbb{C} - I) + \frac{2\mu}{\lambda} \det(\mathbb{C})^{-\frac{\lambda}{2\mu} - 1} dx + \int_{\partial\Omega} \vec{f} \cdot \vec{u} ds$$

where $\mathbb{C} = F^T F$ is the right Cauchy-Green tensor, F is the deformation gradient, μ and λ are the Lamé parameters, and \vec{f} is the force applied to the top face of the beam. A simple discretisation of this energy leads to a non-linear problem that we solve using *PETSc SNES*.

```

from ngsolve import *
import netgen.gui
from netgen.occ import *
import netgen.meshing as ngm
from mpi4py.MPI import COMM_WORLD

if COMM_WORLD.rank == 0:
    d = 0.01
    box = Box ( (-d/2,-d/2,0), (d/2,d/2,0.1) ) + Box( (-d/2, -3*d/2,0.1), (d/2, 3*d/2, 0.
↪1+d) )
    box.faces.Min(Z).name = "bottom"
    box.faces.Max(Z).name = "top"
    mesh = Mesh(OCCGeometry(box).GenerateMesh(maxh=0.05).Distribute(COMM_WORLD))
else:
    mesh = Mesh(ngm.Mesh.Receive(COMM_WORLD))

E, nu = 210, 0.2
mu = E / 2 / (1+nu)
lam = E * nu / ((1+nu)*(1-2*nu))

def C(u):
    F = Id(u.dim) + Grad(u)
    return F.trans * F

def NeoHooke (C):
    # return 0.5*mu*InnerProduct(C-Id(3), C-Id(3))
    return 0.5*mu*(Trace(C-Id(3)) + 2*mu/lam*Det(C)**(-lam/2/mu)-1)

loadfactor = Parameter(1)
force = loadfactor * CF ( (-y, x, 0) )

fes = H1(mesh, order=3, dirichlet="bottom", dim=mesh.dim)

```

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```

u,v = fes.TnT()

a = BilinearForm(fes)
a += Variation(NeoHooke(C(u)).Compile()*dx)
a += ((Id(3)+Grad(u.Trace()))*force)*v*ds("top")

```

Once we have defined the energy and the weak form, we can solve the non-linear problem using *PETSc SNES*. In particular, we will use a Newton method with line search, solving the arising linear systems with a direct solver.

```

from ngsPETSc import NonLinearSolver
gfu_petsc = GridFunction(fes)
gfu_ngs = GridFunction(fes)
gfu_ngs.vec[:] = 0; gfu_petsc.vec[:] = 0
gfu_history_ngs = GridFunction(fes, multidim=0)
gfu_history_petsc = GridFunction(fes, multidim=0)
numsteps = 30
for step in range(numsteps):
    print("step", step)
    loadfactor.Set(720*step/numsteps)
    solver = NonLinearSolver(fes, a=a, objective=False,
                           solverParameters={"snes_type": "newtonls",
                                             "snes_max_it": 200,
                                             "snes_monitor": "",
                                             "ksp_type": "preonly",
                                             "pc_type": "lu",
                                             "snes_linesearch_type": "basic",
                                             "snes_linesearch_damping": 1.0,
                                             "snes_linesearch_max_it": 100})

    gfu_petsc = solver.solve(gfu_petsc)
    solvers.Newton(a, gfu_ngs, printing=True, dampfactor=0.5)
    gfu_history_ngs.AddMultiDimComponent(gfu_ngs.vec)
    gfu_history_petsc.AddMultiDimComponent(gfu_petsc.vec)

```

We compare the performance of the *PETSc SNES* solvers and of *NGSolve*'s own implementation of Newton's method:

Table 1: Performance of different non-linear solvers

Solver	non-linear iteration
NGS Newton (damping=1.0)	Diverged
NGS Newton (damping=0.5)	Diverged
NGS Newton (damping=0.3)	12
PETSc SNES	10

This suggests that while *NGSolve*'s non-linear solver when finely tuned performs as well as *PETSc SNES*, it is more sensitive to the choice of the damping factor. In this case, a damping factor of 0.3 was found to be the best choice.

SOLVING THE LAPLACE EIGENVALUE PROBLEM USING SLEPC EPS

In this tutorial, we explore using *SLEPc EPS* to solve the Laplace eigenvalue problem in primal and mixed formulations. We begin by considering the Poisson eigenvalue problem in primal form, i.e.

$$\text{find } (u, \lambda) \in H_0^1(\Omega) \times \mathbb{R} \text{ s.t. } a(u, v) := \int_{\Omega} \nabla u \cdot \nabla v \, d\vec{x} = \lambda(u, v)_{L^2(\Omega)}, \quad v \in H_0^1(\Omega).$$

Such a discretisation can easily be constructed using NGSolve as follows:

```
from ngsolve import *
import netgen.gui
import netgen.meshing as ngm
import numpy as np
from mpi4py.MPI import COMM_WORLD

mesh = Mesh(unit_square.GenerateMesh(maxh=0.1, comm=COMM_WORLD))

order = 3
fes = H1(mesh, order=order, dirichlet="left|right|top|bottom")
print("Number of degrees of freedom: ", fes.ndof)
u, v = fes.TnT()
a = BilinearForm(grad(u)*grad(v)*dx, symmetric=True)
a.Assemble()
m = BilinearForm(-1*u*v*dx, symmetric=True)
m.Assemble()
```

We then proceed to solve the eigenvalue problem using *SLEPc EPS* which is wrapped by ngsPETSc's `EigenSolver` class. In particular, we will use the SLEPc implementation of locally optimal block preconditioned conjugate gradient. Notice that we have assembled the mass matrix so that it is symmetric negative definite; this is because ngsPETSc `EigenSolver` requires all eigenvalue problems to be written as a polynomial eigenvalue problem, i.e.

$$A\vec{U} - \lambda M\vec{U} = 0$$

where A and M are the stiffness and mass matrices, respectively.

```
from ngsPETSc import EigenSolver
solver = EigenSolver((m, a), fes, 10, solverParameters={"eps_type": "lobpcg", "st_type":
    ↪ "precond"})
solver.solve()
for i in range(10):
    print("Normalised (by pi^2) Eigenvalue ", i, " = ", solver.eigenValue(i)/(np.pi*np.
```

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```

↪pi))
modes, _ = solver.eigenFunctions(list(range(10)))
Draw(modes)

```

Notice that we can access a single eigenvalue using `solver.eigenValue(i)` and the corresponding eigenfunction using `solver.eigenFunction(i)`. If we use `solver.eigenFunctions(indices)` we can access the first 10 eigenfunctions as a multi-dimensional array and we can obtain the corresponding eigenvalues using `solver.eigenValues(indices)`. We now consider a mixed formulation of the Laplace eigenvalue problem, i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{find } (\vec{\sigma}, u, \lambda) \in H(\text{div}, \Omega) \times L^2(\Omega) \times \mathbb{R} \text{ s.t.} \\ &\begin{cases} \int_{\Omega} \vec{\sigma} \cdot \vec{\tau} \, d\vec{x} - \int_{\Omega} u \nabla \cdot \vec{\tau} \, d\vec{x} = 0 & \forall \vec{\tau} \in H(\text{div}, \Omega) \\ \int_{\Omega} \nabla \cdot \vec{\sigma} v \, d\vec{x} = \lambda \int_{\Omega} uv \, d\vec{x} & \forall v \in L^2(\Omega) \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

We can discretise this problem using NGSolve as follows:

```

V = HDiv(mesh, order=order)
Q = L2(mesh, order=order-1)
W = FESpace([V,Q])
print("Number of degrees of freedom: ", W.ndof)
sigma, u = W.TrialFunction()
tau, v = W.TestFunction()
a = BilinearForm(sigma*tau*dx + div(tau)*u*dx + div(sigma)*v*dx)
a.Assemble()

m = BilinearForm(1*u*v*dx)
m.Assemble()

```

We can again solve the eigenvalue problem using ngsPETSc's *EigenSolver* class. The matrix on the right-hand side of the generalised eigenvalue problem now has a large kernel, hence is no longer symmetric positive definite, therefore we can not use LOBPCG as a solver. Instead, we will use a Krylov-Schur solver with a shift-and-invert spectral transformation to target the smallest eigenvalues. Notice that because we are using a shift-and-invert spectral transformation we only need to invert the stiffness matrix which has a trivial kernel since we are using an inf-sup stable discretisation. If we tried to use a simple shift transformation to target the largest eigenvalues we would have run into the error of trying to invert a singular matrix.:

```

solver = EigenSolver((m, a), W, 10,
                    solverParameters={"eps_type": "krylovschur",
                                       "st_type": "sinvert",
                                       "eps_target": 0,
                                       "st_pc_type": "lu",
                                       "st_pc_factor_mat_solver_type": "mumps"})

solver.solve()
for i in range(10):
    print("Normalised (by pi^2) Eigenvalue ", i, " = ", solver.eigenValue(i)/(np.pi*np.
↪pi))
mode, _ = solver.eigenFunction(0)
modeSigma, modeU = mode.components
Draw(modeSigma, mesh, "sigma")
Draw(modeU, mesh, "u")

```

NETGEN LINEAR MESH AND ADAPTIVE MESH REFINEMENT

This tutorial is an improved version of the Netgen tutorial available in the Firedrake documentation, which can be found [here](#). The purpose of this demo is to summarise how to construct and use a Netgen mesh in Firedrake. We will first have a look at how different geometries can be implemented using Netgen, then we will consider as an example the Poisson problem and discuss boundary conditions. Finally, we will show how to use mesh refinement features included in Netgen to construct an adaptive scheme. We begin by importing the necessary libraries

```
from firedrake import *
```

13.1 Constructive Solid Geometry

Using the Constructive Solid Geometry (CSG) features implemented in Netgen, we can construct a geometry starting from basic sets such as rectangles and disks. Let's have a look at an example. First, we need to import the Netgen library required in order to construct a *SplineGeometry*:

```
from netgen.geom2d import SplineGeometry
geo = SplineGeometry()
```

Now using the two of the predefined CSG geometries included in Netgen, a rectangle and a circle, we construct a square with an inscribed disk that we will later flag for refinement, using the *SetMaterial* and *SetDomainMaxH* methods:

```
geo = SplineGeometry()
geo.AddRectangle(p1=(-1, -1),
                p2=(1, 1),
                bc="rectangle",
                leftdomain=1,
                rightdomain=0)
geo.AddCircle(c=(0, 0),
             r=0.5,
             bc="circle",
             leftdomain=2,
             rightdomain=1)

# Flagging for the inside of the disk with a different material IDs
geo.SetMaterial(1, "outer")
geo.SetMaterial(2, "inner")
geo.SetDomainMaxH(2, 0.02)
```

Notice that the *leftdomain* and *rightdomain* attribute in the *AddRectangle* and *AddCircle* methods are used to set a domain index for the domain on the left and right side respectively of the rectangle and circle perimeter. It is worth

mentioning that the perimeters are parametrised in a counterclockwise direction. We can now construct a mesh for the geometry we have defined and save it to a PVD file for visualisation. We will do so using the *GenerateMesh* method inside of the *SplineGeometry* class:

```
ngmsh = geo.GenerateMesh(maxh=0.1)
# Generating a Firedrake mesh from the NetGen mesh
msh = Mesh(ngmsh)
VTKFile("output/MeshExample1.pvd").write(msh)
```


We can also “hardwire” a geometry in Netgen, specifying the points and the splines making the boundary of the domain. In particular we add points to an instance of the *SplineGeometry* class using the method *AppendPoint*, while a spline can be added using the *Append* method. When using the *Append* method we can specify the type of Spline and its boundary label (in this particular case we use the “bnd” tag for all the curves making up the boundary). Here is showed how to construct a “Pacman”-like domain:

```
geo = SplineGeometry()
pnts = [(0, 0), (1, 0), (1, 1),
        (0, 1), (-1, 1), (-1, 0),
        (-1, -1), (0, -1)]
p1, p2, p3, p4, p5, p6, p7, p8 = [geo.AppendPoint(*pnt) for pnt in pnts]
curves = [[["line", p1, p2], "line"],
          [["spline3", p2, p3, p4], "curve"],
          [["spline3", p4, p5, p6], "curve"],
          [["spline3", p6, p7, p8], "curve"],
          [["line", p8, p1], "line"]]
[geo.Append(c, bc=bc) for c, bc in curves]
ngmsh = geo.GenerateMesh(maxh=0.4)
msh = Mesh(ngmsh)
VTKFile("output/MeshExample2.pvd").write(msh)
```


13.2 Poisson Problem

Let's now have a look at some features that can be useful when solving a variational problem using a Netgen mesh. We will consider as an example the Poisson problem with constant source data and homogeneous boundary conditions on the boundary of the PacMan. The only method new to the reader should be the *GetRegionNames* which allows to find the IDs of the boundary we have labeled in Netgen. As usual we begin defining the *FunctionSpace* that will be used in our discretisation, defining trial and test functions and the source data:

```
V = FunctionSpace(msh, "CG", 1)
u = TrialFunction(V)
v = TestFunction(V)

f = Function(V)
x, y = SpatialCoordinate(msh)
f.assign(1)
```

Now we can define the bilinear form and linear function that characterize the weak formulation of the Poisson problem in abstract form, i.e.

$$\text{find } u \in H_0^1(\Omega) \text{ s.t. } a(u, v) := \int_{\Omega} \nabla u \cdot \nabla v \, d\vec{x} = L(v) := \int_{\Omega} f v \, d\vec{x} \quad v \in H_0^1(\Omega).$$

In code this becomes:

```
a = inner(grad(u), grad(v))*dx
L = inner(f, v) * dx
```

Now we are ready to assemble the stiffness matrix for the problem. Since we want to enforce Dirichlet boundary conditions we construct a *DirichletBC* object and we use the *GetRegionNames* method from the Netgen mesh in order to map the label we have given when describing the geometry to the PETSc *DMPLEX* IDs. In particular if we look for the IDs of boundary element labeled either “line” or “curve” we would get:

```

labels = [i+1 for i, name in enumerate(ngmsh.GetRegionNames(codim=1)) if name in ["line",
↪ "curve"]]
bc = DirichletBC(V, 0, labels)
print(labels)

```

We then proceed to solve the problem:

```

sol = Function(V)
solve(a == L, sol, bcs=bc)
VTKFile("output/Poisson.pvd").write(sol)

```

13.3 Adaptive Mesh Refinement

In this section we will discuss how to use the mesh refinement methods wrapped from Netgen C++ interface. In particular we will be considering a Laplace eigenvalue problem on the same PacMan domain presented above, i.e.:

$$\text{Find } u \in H_0^1(\Omega) \text{ and } \lambda \in \mathbb{R} \text{ s.t. } \int_{\Omega} \nabla u \cdot \nabla v \, d\vec{x} = \lambda \int_{\Omega} uv \, d\vec{x} \quad \forall v \in H_0^1(\Omega).$$

This script is based on a code developed by Professor Daniele Boffi and based on a code from Professor Douglas Arnold for the source problem. We begin by defining some quantities of interest such as the desired tolerance, the maximum number of iterations and the exact eigenvalue:

```

from firedrake.petsc import PETSc
from slepc4py import SLEPc
import numpy as np

tolerance = 1e-16
max_iterations = 10
exact = 3.375610652693620492628**2

```

We create a function to solve the eigenvalue problem using SLEPc. We begin initialising the *FunctionSpace*, the bilinear forms and linear functionals needed in the variational problem. Then a SLEPc Eigenvalue Problem Solver (*EPS*) is initialised and set up to use a shift and invert (*SINVERT*) spectral transformation where the preconditioner factorisation is computed using MUMPS:

```

def Solve(msh, labels):
    V = FunctionSpace(msh, "CG", 2)
    u = TrialFunction(V)
    v = TestFunction(V)
    a = inner(grad(u), grad(v))*dx
    m = (u*v)*dx
    uh = Function(V)
    bc = DirichletBC(V, 0, labels)
    A = assemble(a, bcs=bc)
    M = assemble(m, bcs=bc, weight=0.)
    Asc, Msc = A.M.handle, M.M.handle
    E = SLEPc.EPS().create()
    E.setType(SLEPc.EPS.Type.ARNOLDI)
    E.setProblemType(SLEPc.EPS.ProblemType.GHEP)
    E.setDimensions(1, SLEPc.DECIDE)
    E.setOperators(Asc, Msc)

```

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```

ST = E.getST()
ST.setType(SLEPc.ST.Type.SINVERT)
PC = ST.getKSP().getPC()
PC.setType("lu")
PC.setFactorSolverType("mumps")
E.setST(ST)
E.solve()
vr, vi = Asc.getVecs()
with uh.dat.vec_wo as vr:
    lam = E.getEigenpair(0, vr, vi)
return (lam, uh, V)

```

We will also need a function that mark the elements that need to be marked according to an error indicator, i.e.

$$\eta = \sum_{K \in \mathcal{T}_h(\Omega)} h^2 \int_K |\lambda u_h + \Delta u_h|^2 d\vec{x} + \frac{h}{2} \int_{E \subset \partial K} |[\nabla u \cdot n_E]|^2 ds$$

In order to do so we begin by computing the value of the indicator using a piecewise constant function space:

```

def Mark(msh, uh, lam):
    W = FunctionSpace(msh, "DG", 0)
    eta_sq = Function(W)
    w = TestFunction(W)
    f = Constant(1)
    h = CellDiameter(msh) # symbols for mesh quantities
    n = FacetNormal(msh)
    v = CellVolume(msh)

    G = ( # compute cellwise error estimator
        inner(eta_sq / v, w)*dx
        - inner(h**2 * (f + div(grad(uh)))**2, w) * dx
        - inner(h('+)/2 * jump(grad(uh), n)**2, w('+')) * dS
        - inner(h('-')/2 * jump(grad(uh), n)**2, w('-')) * dS
    )

    # Each cell is an independent 1x1 solve, so Jacobi is exact
    sp = {"mat_type": "matfree", "ksp_type": "richardson", "pc_type": "jacobi"}
    solve(G == 0, eta_sq, solver_parameters=sp)
    eta = Function(W).interpolate(sqrt(eta_sq)) # compute eta from eta^2

    with eta.dat.vec_ro as eta_: # compute estimate for error in energy norm
        error_est = sqrt(eta_.dot(eta_))
    markers = Function(W)

    # We decide to refine an element if its error indicator
    # is within a fraction of the maximum cellwise error indicator

    # Access storage underlying our Function
    # (a PETSc Vec) to get maximum value of eta
    with eta.dat.vec_ro as eta_:
        eta_max = eta_.max()[1]

    theta = 0.5

```

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```

should_refine = conditional(gt(eta, theta*eta_max), 1, 0)
markers.interpolate(should_refine)
return markers

```

It is now time to define the solve, mark and refine loop that is at the heart of the adaptive method described here:

```

for i in range(max_iterations):
    print("level {}".format(i))
    lam, uh, V = Solve(msh, labels)
    mark = Mark(msh, uh, lam)
    msh = msh.refine_marked_elements(mark)
    VTKFile("output/AdaptiveMeshRefinement.pvd").write(uh)

```

Note that the mesh conforms to the CAD geometry as it is adaptively refined.

13.4 Constructive Solid Geometry in 3D

In this section we will focus our attention on three dimensional constructive solid geometry. In particular we will look at the operators $+$, $-$, $*$, which have been overridden to have a special meaning when applied to two instances of the class *CSGeometry*. It is important to notice that the same operators can be used also when working with a *SplineGeometry* and their action will have the same meaning that is presented here. The $+$, $-$, $*$ operators have respectively the meaning of union, set difference, and intersection. We will build a cube using the planes intersection and remove from it a portion of sphere:

```

from netgen.csg import *
left = Plane(Pnt(0, 0, 0), Vec(-1, 0, 0))
right = Plane(Pnt(1, 1, 1), Vec(1, 0, 0))
front = Plane(Pnt(0, 0, 0), Vec(0, -1, 0))
back = Plane(Pnt(1, 1, 1), Vec(0, 1, 0))

```

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```

bot = Plane(Pnt(0, 0, 0), Vec(0, 0, -1))
top = Plane(Pnt(1, 1, 1), Vec(0, 0, 1))
cube = left * right * front * back * bot * top
cube.bc("cube")
sphere = Sphere(Pnt(0.6, 0.6, 0.6), 0.5)
geo = CSGeometry()
geo.Add(cube-sphere)
ngmsh = geo.GenerateMesh(maxh=0.1)
msh = Mesh(ngmsh)
VTKFile("output/MeshExample3.pvd").write(msh)

```

13.5 Open Cascade Technology

Last we will have a look at the Netgen Open Cascade Technology interface, which has been recently included. We will follow the tutorial presented in the [NetGen docs](#), which itself comes from the OCCT tutorial [here](#). The idea is to draw a “flask” using the OCCT interface and solve the linear elasticity equations to compute the stress tensor on the flask subject to gravity. We begin importing the Netgen Open Cascade interface and constructing the bottom of the flask using many different method such as *Axis*, *Face*, *Pnt*, *Segment*, ... (all the details this methods can be found in [NetGen docs](#))

```

from netgen.occ import *
myHeight = 70
myWidth = 50
myThickness = 30
pnt1 = Pnt(-myWidth / 2., 0, 0)
pnt2 = Pnt(-myWidth / 2., -myThickness / 4., 0)
pnt3 = Pnt(0, -myThickness / 2., 0)
pnt4 = Pnt(myWidth / 2., -myThickness / 4., 0)
pnt5 = Pnt(myWidth / 2., 0, 0)
seg1 = Segment(pnt1, pnt2)
arc = ArcOfCircle(pnt2, pnt3, pnt4)
seg2 = Segment(pnt4, pnt5)
wire = Wire([seg1, arc, seg2])
mirrored_wire = wire.Mirror(Axis((0, 0, 0), X))
w = Wire([wire, mirrored_wire])
f = Face(w)
f.bc("bottom")

```

Once the bottom part of the flask has been constructed we then extrude it to create the main body. We now construct the neck of the flask and fuse it with the main body:

```

body = f.Extrude(myHeight*Z)
body = body.MakeFillet(body.edges, myThickness / 12.0)
neckax = Axes(body.faces.Max(Z).center, Z)
myNeckRadius = myThickness / 4.0
myNeckHeight = myHeight / 10
neck = Cylinder(neckax, myNeckRadius, myNeckHeight)
body = body + neck
fmax = body.faces.Max(Z)
thickbody = body.MakeThickSolid([fmax], -myThickness / 50, 1.e-3)

```

Last we are left to construct the threading of the flask neck and fuse it to the rest of the flask body. In order to do this we are going to need the value of pi, which we grab from the Python math package:

```
import math
cyl1 = Cylinder(neckax, myNeckRadius * 0.99, 1).faces[0]
cyl2 = Cylinder(neckax, myNeckRadius * 1.05, 1).faces[0]
aPnt = Pnt(2 * math.pi, myNeckHeight / 2.0)
aDir = Dir(2 * math.pi, myNeckHeight / 4.0)
anAx2d = gp_Ax2d(aPnt, aDir)
aMajor = 2 * math.pi
aMinor = myNeckHeight / 10
arc1 = Ellipse(anAx2d, aMajor, aMinor).Trim(0, math.pi)
arc2 = Ellipse(anAx2d, aMajor, aMinor/4).Trim(0, math.pi)
seg = Segment(arc1.start, arc1.end)
wire1 = Wire([Edge(arc1, cyl1), Edge(seg, cyl1)])
wire2 = Wire([Edge(arc2, cyl2), Edge(seg, cyl2)])
threading = ThruSections([wire1, wire2])
bottle = thickbody + threading
geo = OCCGeometry(bottle)
```

As usual, we generate a mesh for the described geometry and use the Firedrake-Netgen interface to import as a PETSc DMPLEX:

```
ngmsh = geo.GenerateMesh(maxh=5)
msh = Mesh(ngmsh)
VTKFile("output/MeshExample4.pvd").write(msh)
```


HIGH-ORDER MESHES

This tutorial is an improved version of the Netgen tutorial available in the Firedrake documentation, which can be found [here](#). It is possible to construct high-order meshes for a geometry constructed in Netgen. In order to do so we need to use the `curve_field` method of a Firedrake `Mesh` object generated from a Netgen mesh. In particular, we need to pass the degree of the polynomial field we want to use to parametrise the coordinates of the domain to the `curve_field` method, which will return a `Function` constructed on a DG space for this purpose.

```
from firedrake import *
from netgen.occ import WorkPlane, OCCGeometry
import netgen
from mpi4py import MPI

wp = WorkPlane()
if COMM_WORLD.rank == 0:
    for i in range(6):
        wp.Line(0.6).Arc(0.4, 60)
    shape = wp.Face()
    ngmesh = OCCGeometry(shape, dim=2).GenerateMesh(maxh=1.)
else:
    ngmesh = netgen.libngpy._meshing.Mesh(2)
mesh = Mesh(Mesh(ngmesh, comm=COMM_WORLD).curve_field(4))
VTKFile("output/MeshExample5.pvd").write(mesh)
```

High-order meshes are also supported in three dimensions; we just need to specify the correct dimension when constructing the `OCCGeometry` object. We will now show how to solve the Poisson problem on a high-order mesh, of order 3, for the unit sphere.

```
from netgen.occ import Sphere, Pnt
import netgen
from mpi4py import MPI

if COMM_WORLD.rank == 0:
    shape = Sphere(Pnt(0,0,0), 1)
    ngmesh = OCCGeometry(shape, dim=3).GenerateMesh(maxh=1.)
else:
    ngmesh = netgen.libngpy._meshing.Mesh(3)
mesh = Mesh(Mesh(ngmesh).curve_field(3))
# Solving the Poisson problem
VTKFile("output/MeshExample6.pvd").write(mesh)
x, y, z = SpatialCoordinate(mesh)
V = FunctionSpace(mesh, "CG", 3)
f = Function(V).interpolate(1+0*x)
```

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```
u = TrialFunction(V)
v = TestFunction(V)
a = inner(grad(u), grad(v)) * dx
l = inner(f, v) * dx

sol = Function(V)

bc = DirichletBC(V, 0.0, [1])
A = assemble(a, bcs=bc)
b = assemble(l)
bc.apply(b)
solve(A, sol, b, solver_parameters={"ksp_type": "cg", "pc_type": "lu"})

VTKFile("output/Sphere.pvd").write(sol)
```


It is also possible to construct high-order meshes using the *SplineGeometry*, *CSG2d* and *CSG* classes.

```
from netgen.geom2d import CSG2d, Circle, Rectangle
import netgen
from mpi4py import MPI
```

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```
if COMM_WORLD.rank == 0:
    geo = CSG2d()
    circle = Circle(center=(1,1), radius=0.1, bc="curve").Maxh(0.01)
    rect = Rectangle(pmin=(0,1), pmax=(1,2),
                    bottom="b", left="l", top="t", right="r")
    geo.Add(rect-circle)
    ngmesh = geo.GenerateMesh(maxh=0.2)
else:
    ngmesh = netgen.libngpy._meshing.Mesh(2)
mesh = Mesh(Mesh(ngmesh, comm=COMM_WORLD).curve_field(2))
VTKFile("output/MeshExample7.pvd").write(mesh)
```


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